

**VIDEO CONFERENCING: PROFESSIONAL AND ACADEMIC DEVELOPMENT
OF DISTRICT INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING**

Dr. Naik Tarsing

Assistant Professor

S.M.T. Government College of Education, Kolhapur.

Dr. Babasaheb Kadam

Joint Director

Kokan Region, Panvel.

Abstract-

This article studies the role of videoconferencing in development of District Institute of Education and Training (DIET). A supreme effort is needed on a high priority basis, to improve the situation of academic, administrative and professional development of teacher training institution. The virtual studies is not sufficiently realized that courses for professional subjects contain a great deal of matter which is either out of date or has little relevance to a District Institute of Education and Training work. Videoconferencing is that a nation wide programme of District Institute of Education and Training improvement. The potential of videoconferencing to enrich all the District Institute of Education and Training all over the Maharashtra.

Keyword- District Institute of Education and Training (DIET), videoconferencing, academic, administrative, professional development.

Introduction-

The national policy on education recognized the continuity and inseparability of pre and in service teacher education and recommended permanent educational mechanisms for it. As a consequence District Institute of Education and Training were established in Maharashtra. Throughout the world, in-service teacher education has acquired an important position for the improvement in the quality of teachers. The great need to improve standard of education at the school stage, videoconferencing is that a nation wide programme of school improvement should be developed in all District Institute of Education and Training. It involves every educational institution and all the social factors connect with it-its teachers, students and local community and unless it provides the necessary inducements to make them put in their best efforts. For various reasons this involvement does not take place and the motivation is not created at present. A videoconferencing is a sound programme of development of

District Institute of Education and Training. The traditional programme of professional development will be perpetuate. In a situation like the present when new and dynamic methods of instruction are needed such as attitude becomes an obstacle to progress. It can be modified only by effective professional development which will initiate the teachers to the needed reevaluation in teaching and lay the foundations for their future professional growth.

Unfortunately the professional development of teachers has been comparatively neglected. Its significance was stressed by the University Education Commission(1949),the Secondary Education Commission (1953) and the international team on teachers and curricula in secondary schools(1954). (Leask & Pachler, 1999, p. 106).

Through the videoconferencing teachers learn the professional competencies and performance skills in a particular context which goes on changing. Preparing them to adjust to the new social and educational context and demands of the emerging concerns require their re-education and additional inputs. Certainly, early evidence did point to videoconferencing being dominated by the lecture format (Dallat, Frazer, Livingston, & Robinson, 1992; Freeman, 1998; Mason, 1998; Oliver & Reeves, 1996). It is thus susceptible to all of the reputed drawbacks of that mode of teaching (Bates, 2005). Even a recent study suggested that the videoconference 'invites the delivery of lectures' but in an inferior way: 'videoconferencing as a medium offers less than the lecture in terms of pedagogy, and wins mainly on the logistical value of bringing people together across a distance' (Laurillard, 2002, p. 158).

The learning can be further extended by recording the videoconferences and using the videotapes as classroom resources. Video streaming can also be used to archive recordings, thus enabling more people to benefit via the Internet. (Arnold *et al* 2002, p. 166). Videoconferencing can also greatly enrich the professional development of teachers. They too can be put into contact with experts and with their peers, either elsewhere in their own country or anywhere else in the world. This leads not only to an enhancement of their continuous learning as professionals, but also to a significant saving of their time and energy. It is also extremely cost-effective. Several seminars, workshops, conference, selection grade training were held and study groups were appointed to discuss improvement in primary school have remained isolated from the main stream of the academic life of the university as well as from the daily problems of the schools.

The social segregation that now takes place in our primary and secondary schools and pointed out that such segregation should be eliminated if education is to be made a powerful instrument of national development in general and social and national integration

in particular. From this point of view, the videoconferencing adoption of the neighborhood school concept. First at the lower primary stage and then at the higher primary and teacher training institution. Videoconferencing provide the neighborhood school and teacher training institution concept implies that each teacher training institution should be attended by all teacher in the neighborhood irrespective of caste, creed community ,religion, economic condition or social status. So that these would be no segregation in teacher training institution . Videoconferencing provide good education, training, selection grade, curriculum refresher course,orientation programme to training to teacher, teacher educator primary teachers, qualities maintain continuous interaction between teacher-teacher,student-teacher,parent-teacher-headmaster-student-resourceperson, administrative, principal-teacher educator and SCERT-

Through videoconferencing the SCERT interact to district level pre-service and in-service training for elementary school teachers,teacher training institution. To organize and support teacher professional development and leadership development programs for teacher educators,Head Masters, senior teachers, and School Management Committees on a continued basis. To address district specific material development, action research programs for special groups in the District. To develop district academic plans and monitoring the quality of schools and teaching. To design interventions for direct support to schools and work with special groups in the district.

Videoconferencing is a two way broadcast system in which learners teacher training institution principal, administrative staff teachers can interact with the administration, professional development of teacher educators, new innovations in education, action research programme through the internet. It is a powerful medium of instruction for distance

education. Videoconferencing involves the use of many media and allows interactive group communication by means of a two way broadcast .

When groups of training teacher institutions, primary & secondary schools teacher, students over a large area of the country and it is possible for them to interact with their teachers personally, then learning through videoconferencing .Many more number of institutions can be communicate through the videoconferencing. It is a cheap means of instruction. In videoconferencing time table can be adjusted according to the availability and suitability of learners scattered over wide range of area. Learner a or administrator, teacher educators get answer of their questions immediately from the experts and their problem is solved . In this way they get immediate feedback. Teachers should be made aware of the new and emerging issues and their new roles. The programme should not be reduced to a monologue, of the resource persons. It should be a dialogue between the participating teachers and the resource persons. Group discussion ,seminars and workshops should be arranged .All participant also encouraged to act as resource persons.

Objective-

1. To develop and put in place an institutional mechanism for monitoring and assessment.
2. To develop district academic plans and monitoring the quality of schools and teaching.

3. To appraise the work of the primary school and to give suitable criticism of work being carried on.
4. To develop in teaches a growing recognition of the factors that affect learning.
5. To organize pre-service and in-service training at an advanced level.

Methodology-

In this research study, survey method was adopted to study the role of videoconferencing in professional development of District Institute of Education and Training. The questionnaires were structured on District Institute of Education and Training interest about videoconferencing, professional development. Analysis plan was prepared and with statistical inputs analysis was done.

Sample of the study -

The role of videoconferencing in District Institute of Education and Training professional development of significant research and so the study aims to make a contribution to the field at improving the quality of the District Institute of Education and Training. For the present study the purposive sampling method was used for the selection of District Institute of Education and Training and random sampling method was used to select the stratification has been done on the basis of administration and professional development. The sample consisted of 1 District Institute of Education and Training out of 33 DIET in Maharashtra.

The details of sample are given in table

Sr.No.	Name of post	Posted
1	Principal	1
2	Sr. Lecturer	0
3	Lecturer	6
4	Suptd.	1
5	Accountant	1

6	Technician	1
7	Steno	2
8	Sta. Asstt.	1
9	Workshop.Asstt.	1
10	Librarian	1
11	Jr. Clerk	2
Total		17

Conclusion-

1. 98.74% District Institute of Education and Training lecture are agree videoconferencing provides general support to the teachers, whereas it carries a definite part of the curriculum to the students at regular intervals.
2. The principal agree to continue to be nodal institution at the district level to transact pre-service and in-service training for elementary school teachers.
3. 98% employee of District Institute of Education and Training suggest to organize and support teacher professional development and leadership development programs for Head Masters, senior teachers, and School Management Committees on a continued basis.
4. Develop DIET as an Education Resource Centre for the district in conjunctions with all primary and secondary schools.
5. Available the district specific material development offices, action research programs for special groups in the District.
6. 50% technician and lectures suggest Networking with national, regional, state, district and sub-district level institutions/ Organizations involves in school education and teacher Education.
7. Designing interventions for direct support to schools and work with special groups in the District. Studies on status of education, education assessment, and documentation.

Suggestion –

- 1.To conduct professional development program District Institute of Education and Training lectures according to experience and for different subjects of secondary school teachers.
2. To provide videoconferencing facilities to District Institute of Education and Training at all levels and to use in professional development programme.
- 3.To organize summer courses in subject content as well as in professional development.
- 4.To work in close collaboration with a state levels school of all types with a view to developing research and evolving better curricula and techniques of teaching.
- 5.Making adequate provision for the continuing professional development of all District Institute of Education and Training.
- 6.Creating appropriate agencies both at the centre and in the states for the maintenance of standards in professional development of primary school teachers.
- 7.Making collaboration between secondary schools and teacher training institutions could advantageous be extended beyond the professional development course.
- 8.Selected teachers from various schools could join videoconferencing from time to time and participate ,also in evolving new plans of work and methods of teaching.
- 9.Monitoring and Evaluation Procedures for quality Education.
10. To consolidate and strengthen the existing institutional structures and to Address the problems of untrained teachers.
- 11.To expand institutional Capacity to provide training for in-service secondary school teachers to fulfill requirements and link elementary teacher education with higher education system.
12. Greater use of ICT in teacher education institutions

Reference -

- Arnold, T., Cayley, S. & Griffith, M. (2002).Videoconferencing in the classroom: communications technology across the curriculum.
- Best, John W. & Khan, James V. (1996), "Research in Education", New Delhi; Prentice Hall of India Private Limited, 7th Edition.
- Brown, K.G. : (2001). Using computers to deliver training : Which employees learn and why? Personal Psychology, 54, 271-296.

- Brown, Johnes, Lewis, Richard, B. Harclerod, Fred N. : (1983), "Instructional Technology Media and Methods" New York; Mac Graw Hill Book Co.
- Buch, M.B. : (1983), "Fourth Survey of Research in Education "New Delhi; National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- Buch, M.B. : (1992) , "Fifth Survey of Research in Education, "New Delhi; National Devon: Devon Curriculum Services. Austin, R., Abbott, L., Mulkeen, A. & Metcalfe, N. (2003).The global classroom: collaboration and cultural awareness in the north and south of Irelan.Coleraine: University of Ulster.Bilton-Ward, A. C. (1997).Virtual teaching—an educator’s guide. Waco, TX: CORD Communications
- Inc.Bilton-Ward, A. C. & Young, M. (1998).Exemplary applications of videoconferencing in education
Waco, TX: CORD Communications Inc.
- Bruce, B. C. & Levin, J. A. (1997). Educational Technology: Media for Inquiry, Communication,Construction, and Expression.
- Coventry, L. (1998).Video conferencing in higher education. Edinburgh: Institute for Computer Based Learning, Heriot Watt University.
- Gardner, H. (1983).Frames of mind: the theory of multiple intelligences. New York: Basic Books.
- Heath, M. J. & Halznagel, D. (2002, October).Interactive videoconferencing: a literature review.
- Prepared for the K-12 National Symposium for Interactive Videoconferencing Dallas, TX.